

ROLE OF TEACHER EDUCATOR'S TOWARDS A LEARNING SOCIETY

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Abstract

The present paper explains the role of teacher educations in a learning society. It describes that teachers who are being educated today will have to develop major part of their life to education during 21st century. If the present state of explosion of knowledge continues, in a few years, teachers will find themselves in a world where their present knowledge and teaching skills, to an extent would become obsolete they will have to face the challenges of information technology and use them meaningfully. So present paper explains how the teacher educators prepare our teachers to face the challenge & to cope up with the challenging scenario.

Key words: Learning Society, Teacher Educator, Profession.

Introduction

"The destiny of India is being shaped in its classrooms." This is the first remark which begins the Kothari commission report. Looking to the history of mankind we find that each century has witnessed different social transformations. Accordingly, educational processes no doubt, a sound programming of education plays a significant role in nations development and the quality of education programme is greatly determined by the quality of education, it is necessary to have a sound programme of professional education of teachers.

There are various agencies to evolve a comprehensive and systematic organizational framework for inservice education and training of teachers like NCERT, NIEPA, DIETS and many others. They help in extending the disciplines in behavioral sciences through tracing and research. NCTE as an independent body opens a new hope and era by laying down standards and guidelines also evolving various criteria for better performance of teachers and teacher education institutions.

"An educational system can only be as good as its teachers. Teacher training, both preservices and inservice teachers must be reformed so that teachers with students and to facilitate their development it is felt that preserves training focuses almost exclusively on knowledge acquisition with little attention to pedagogy. Instructional practices and classroom management skills" (NCTE, 1997).

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The development in the application and dissemination of knowledge and information technology have been changing the demands in education. It was felt that teacher training is a crucial factor in meeting these demands but at the same time that the teacher training institutes needed to be reformed the four goals were set as:-

- The development of a common core curriculum for both primary and secondary education teacher.
- The formation of regional centers for co-operation in teacher training.
- The enhancement of human resource management.
- The establishment of innovation centers for ICT.

The impact of the use of information and communication technology in education will not be limited to the teacher educations involved in teaching-learning process but will also change the institutional infrastructure, relations and patterns of behaviour within the education system and even the content of education therefore an important focus in initial teacher education must be an equipping teacher with pedagogy that enables then to integrate relevant information and Communication technology with the process of teaching and learning.

In teaching profession, a teacher has to perform multiple activities like teaching, evaluating, communicating, guiding and counseling the students, organizing co-curricular activities, participate in community programmers, diagnose and remedy students problems etc. together with activities which are intrinsic to teaching and learning. This needs perfection in academic and professional preparation of teachers and teacher educators. So the need and importance of teacher education is:

- To educate teachers in Organizing learning resources.
- To accomplish them for effective curriculum teaching strategies.
- To educate them to evaluate the outcomes of learning.
- To educate them to organize and guide a variety of curricular activities.
- To endow them the quality to Organize and participate in programmes of community service and development.-

The national curriculum for teacher Education (1988); "A frame work has given some basic principals and considerations for developing teacher education curriculum design. It has also provided broad directions in which desired changes can be brought about in the content and process of preservice education at elementary, secondary and also at pre school stages.

- Teacher education programmers are meant for professional preparation of teachers and so they should provide for a comprehensive coverage of professional knowledge, values ad skills and have a strong functional orientation.
- Preservices teacher education has to be considered as an induction initiation process for further growth.

- The programme of teacher education should be flexible to accommodate local and regional needs.
- The programme should provide a continuous and comprehensive evaluation.

Teaching As A Profession

Now a days teachers professional development is an impotent issue in the area of teacher education. It is stated in several ways. There should be professionalization of teaching at every level i.e. from primary stage to higher education. Accordingly to websites New world Dictionary of the American Language, "A Profession is a vocation or occupation requiring advanced training in some liberal or science and usually involving mental rather than manual work, as teaching, engineering, writing etc".

Teaching is a profession that can be described as an Occupation which provides highly specialized intellectual services. Teaching profession is a body of erudite knowledge, a set of attitudes and a techniques which is applied to the service of making through an educated group;

- It is as organized body of intellectual theory constantly expanding by research.
- It is an intellectual technique which has practical applications.
- It needs a long period of training and certification.

Teaching has always been a profession which makes human beings; a profession with its own unique traditions; a true profession with an organization that regulates admission of members, exerts control over them and secure for them certain rights & privileges. It also fulfills certain Conditions, which supports it as a profession likes teachers are Organized at national, state and local levels; teaching requires careful skills and understanding.

No profession completely meets all the standards discussed above, each has its own areas of weakness. Educators have taken lengthy strides toward their professional goals, but they have not yet reached them. Professional development has been repaid but it has been uniform throughout the nation in some communities, institutions and instructional areas, teachers have reached greater professional status then they have in others. In future even greater gains may be enforce greater control over admission to, preparation for, and continuation in teaching profession to maintain professional standards.

Professional Growth of Teachers

Every living substance is growing and continuous growth is insign of survival, a teacher who is not growing is decaying and as a professional person a teachers learning is essential for growth in his professional life. The growth comprises of a frame of reference. Which includes a point of departure, directions and further goals. A teacher who is able to demonstrate that he is doing a better and more efficient job than what he did in the past has been able to claim the rightful share of his professional upgrading. Ideally a teacher must learn something new almost everyday, teach some thing new almost every days; teach old topics in a new way and should create some new knowledge almost every day

to show that is growing. The professional development of a teacher consist of three component:

- Development of pedagogical skills of teacher i.e. he should become a better communicator of knowledge with the knowledge of learning.
- Development of mastering of a subject by the teacher i.e. the teacher should know much more than what he is teaching.
- Development of the teacher as a member of the teaching profession.

Samuel Bower Sinclair held that “During professional learning and training the courses the teacher gains an insight which will enable him to originate his own methods, to reconstruct his own experience at every step so as to react in the best possible way and also at the same time gain impulse for further development.

Learning Society

Learning and learning to learn are two aspects of learner development that the teacher has attended. All methods thus address to these two mutually dependent aspects of cognition. A teacher without suitable education and training in the science of learning and art of teaching cannot practice the profession of teaching effectively.

The development to a new stade in the relationship between education and society implies a transformation of education as well as a new definition of education. If we accept the view that society is transforming from an industrial stage to an information stage there is no doubt that this information society will generate completely new definitions of education. These new definitions will come from the learning needs and possibilities in the information society for example, Self instructional teaching material play a “front line” role in the learning process with actual teacher playing the role of tutor support counseling on managerial as shown:

The learning process takes place at the cross section of two dimensions as a result of balance between the four forces; teacher, learner, content and material. A learning process is the result of both structural condition derived from leaving infrastructure and personal characteristics of teacher-student involved.

As we move from learning society every human activity will require contributions from experts, and this will place the entire sector of education in sharp focus. Although the priorities which are being assigned to-day to the task of "Education for all" will continue to be preponderant, the country will have to prepare itself to invest more and more on all levels of education. There is a need of creating a learning society on the four pillars of education i.e. learning to know, learning to do, learning to live together, learning to be. There is felt need to think globally and to act locally and this is the duty of teacher educators to prepare teachers on these concepts.

Conclusion

From seeing teacher educators as a bearer of knowledge to be communicated to seeking them as stimulators of knowledge to be constructed and developed by pupils through the learning experiences; from being believers that pupils will remain different; from being executors of teaching procedures recommended by others to design and/or adaptors of such procedures and from being isolated individuals in their classrooms to being coworkers collaborating in the improvement of teaching and learning. The teacher s educators role will be shifted from teachers to knowledge workers, consultants and councilors. The time may come when students may come to teachers very rarely, which may create a downfall of face to face teacher education program teacher educators should internalize their changing role and make themselves ready for the change. So it is better to prepare our teachers to face the challenge & to copy with the changing scenario, which can enrich the status of teacher education at all, its forms.

References

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